

ASSESSING THE TRAINING OF HEU’ STUDENTS IN THE FIELD OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGY: ON THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN

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***Abstract.** This article aims to develop a pedagogical strategy for preparing students for vocational education. The author presents the structure, components and conditions of preparation of students of higher education institutions for professional and pedagogical activity on the basis of a competency approach. The experimental sites were obtained in higher education institutions in Uzbekistan.*

***Keywords:** HEU’, pedagogical strategy, professional education, pedagogical activity, competitive approach.*

1. Introduction

According to the pedagogical theories of pedagogical scientists and practitioners of the world, in the development of professional readiness of students in higher professional education, the continuity of education, logic and need-based, the effectiveness of the education system the method is inextricably linked with the creation of a technical-technological, creative environment and educational space for the full realization of its hidden abilities through the use of its tools. Therefore, there is a need to ensure the continuity of teaching in vocational education, the development of educational processes and the orientation of the content of specialized disciplines to practical skills.

As part of the reforms in the higher education system in Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved the "Concept for the development of the higher education system until 2030". The concept includes "ensuring the coherence and consistency of general secondary, secondary special and higher education programs in order to achieve continuity of education." Special attention was paid to the formation of skills of students in the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process, improving the infrastructure of pedagogical education, the provision of highly qualified professional teachers who have learned foreign languages in all secondary schools in the region. "Everywhere you look today, the tide of protectionist sentiment is flowing. We can respond to this fierce competition only through the widespread introduction of modern science, high technology and innovation". Therefore, in the research work carried out in the higher education system, it is important to design and implement pedagogical strategies in line with modern educational trends to ensure the quality and effectiveness of teaching, high intellectual potential and professional competence of specialists and their worthy place in the labor market.

Improving the methodological and scientific-methodological framework for the development of professional training of students in modern education on the basis of pedagogical-strategic design, the development of knowledge, skills and abilities of teachers in the pedagogical process of digital technologies, multimedia, advanced pedagogical technologies, Cultural Organization (UNESCO), International Project on Technical and Vocational Education (Germany), Educational Organization e-DEKA, Aghioi Theodoroi (Almyrra), Korinth Greece

(Greece), Dubnica Institute of Technology in Dubnica nad Váhom Slovakia (Slovakia), University of Research is being conducted in higher education institutions such as Management Education (Ukraine), Gazi University (Turkey), Universitas Negeri Malang, Academy of Education (Russia), Tashkent State Pedagogical University (Uzbekistan).

The following scientific results have been achieved on the problem of improving the professional and pedagogical training of students in the field of vocational education on the basis of strategic design: advanced teaching methods in vocational education and professional competencies of graduates based on the integration of digital technologies (Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)); Mechanisms for diagnosing the readiness of graduates in the technical field for professional activity and the development of professional competencies of graduates of employers in the manufacturing sector on the basis of training tools have been improved (University of Management Education), as well as Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology (Uzbekistan).

The purpose of given article is to improve the pedagogical strategy of preparing students for professional activities in the field of vocational education.

2. Methodology

Areas of preparation of students for professional and pedagogical activity are developing with the most advanced methods and directions recognized worldwide. Today, new concepts and theories are being developed in connection with other areas of scientific research in this area, which are waiting for their widespread application. The direction of preparing students for professional and pedagogical activities in higher education is developing in harmony with the development of vocational and pedagogical and technical education as an integral part of general pedagogy, which is relatively young and developing in many areas. The main goal of the new stage of preparing students for professional and pedagogical activity is to train specialists who will be able to adapt to the changing world production conditions, to raise our economy to a new level and to develop a creative approach, independent thinking and application.

Deal to these we make up structure of preparing students in professional activity through competitive approach. (Pic.1.)

Pic.1. Preparing students in professional activity through competitive approach

It is one of the most important requirements for the qualification of a university student ready for a high level of professionalism, which reflects the level of competence in the chosen professional and pedagogical field. According to A.A.Kirsanov, "Preparing students for professional and pedagogical activities in higher education" is an aspect of the student's compliance with the requirements of the employer as a future specialist, high qualification and skills in professional and pedagogical activities, the level of competence in the chosen professional and pedagogical field.

Fig.2. Components of preparation of students for professional and pedagogical activity and conditions affecting it

The study identified the components of preparing students for professional and pedagogical activities: the level of knowledge, socio-personal and professional-pedagogical and conditions that affect the quality of preparation of students for professional-pedagogical activities (see Figure 2).

The development of preparation of students for professional activity in higher education, the pedagogical process in the professional formation of the specialist is carried out in the professional-educational space, which is a factor in determining the personal development, self-awareness, professional orientation of students in higher education.

3. Conclusion

In our study, professional education is given priority as a leading factor in improving the preparation of students for professional activities. In our opinion, the need to combine professional education in higher education stems from the formation of professional-pedagogical, personal and competent qualities of the graduate - a future specialist.

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